

“Generating fuel and oxygen using a system that relies on solar energy and atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂)”

2025

Inventor's name:

Mohammed Falah Hassan Al-Dhafiri

Title:

Generating fuel and oxygen using a system that relies on solar energy and atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂).

Abstract:

The fuel and oxygen (O₂) generation in this innovation relies on sunlight, carbon dioxide (CO₂), and conventionally treated wastewater. This increases atmospheric oxygen, leading to a moderate climate and also provides an important fuel for human use. Therefore, the main problem, the impact of increased carbon dioxide (CO₂) on the climate, is addressed using a system that utilizes three main sources: sunlight, conventionally treated wastewater, and the abundant carbon dioxide in the atmosphere. This process goes through several stages to provide fuel and oxygen (O₂). Thus, increased atmospheric oxygen leads to a moderate climate.

Introduction:

In light of the challenges and difficulties facing the world, the problem of climate change is becoming increasingly complex. This has led to numerous problems and difficulties, including significant temperature fluctuations.

The core of the problem lies in the increase in carbon dioxide in the atmosphere resulting from the burning of fossil fuels and other causes. Another major problem is the scarcity of fresh water.

Designing a system that reduces carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere and produces oxygen (O₂) has become a pressing and important issue to reduce current emissions. Therefore, work has begun

on carbon capture processes. However, the main problem is that these processes require high energy and increased complexity, which reduces their efficiency and makes them difficult to rely on, especially if they do not rely on clean, renewable energy, which results in low cost and zero pollution. This has led to an urgent need for a system that relies on renewable energy and combines a range of solutions. This innovation presents a design that combines solutions to all of these problems, relying on three main inputs: sunlight, atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂), and conventionally treated wastewater.

Solar energy is essential for generating electricity (photovoltaic cells) and heat (thermal collectors). Wastewater is a source of pollution and an important part of the system. In this system, wastewater becomes an essential part of the water supply process. After filtering the water of all its complex components, oxygen (O₂) is separated from hydrogen (H₂).

Objectives:

The goal is to design a system that absorbs carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and converts it into oxygen, leading to climate moderation and the provision of fuel produced from chemical processes (methanol) using solar energy, which is the sole source of energy in this system. This system also achieves environmental benefits, including reducing global warming by reducing carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, and achieving economic benefits by increasing demand for renewable energy technologies instead of fossil fuels.

How it works:

This system operates through multiple processes, divided into several stages:

1. Energy Production Stage:

Solar panels, which are currently widely deployed, are used to produce the electrical energy the system desperately needs. This is accomplished by converting sunlight into electrical energy, as well as by generating thermal energy from solar energy using solar thermal collectors (STCs), required in the water treatment unit.

2. Water Treatment Unit:

This unit undergoes several stages after conventional wastewater treatment. The first stage is ultrafiltration, which removes large particles, viruses, and bacteria from the wastewater resulting from conventional treatment. The water then reaches the membrane distillation (DM) stage. This stage requires solar thermal energy, which comes from the STCs. The highly purified water then enters a storage tank.

3. Carbon Absorption Stage:

Direct carbon dioxide absorbers (DACs) are used to absorb carbon dioxide from the air. The carbon dioxide is then purified and prepared for chemical synthesis.

4. Fuel and Oxygen Production Stage:

Electricity generated from solar panels is fed into an electrolyzer, which separates highly purified water into hydrogen (H₂) and oxygen (O₂). This separation occurs because hydrogen must chemically react to produce methanol, releasing oxygen into the atmosphere to regulate the climate.

The carbon dioxide (CO₂) extracted from the atmosphere and purified by absorption devices, along with the hydrogen separated from the water, is then introduced into a chemical reactor (RC), where they react in the presence of a suitable catalyst and at a suitable temperature to produce a suitable fuel (methanol).

As shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 : schematic diagram

Challenges:

There are some challenges, including:

1. Economic cost: The relatively high cost of DAC and electrolyzer technologies.
2. Energy efficiency: The need for significant energy, so solar panels must produce significant energy to cover the energy required to operate the system.

Future work:

Research for more efficient and less expensive catalysts and develop more efficient technical membranes.

Conclusion:

This system represents a significant development in increasing the oxygen content in the atmosphere and maximizing the use of carbon dioxide to provide biofuel for vital uses, such as jet fuel and others, by utilizing solar energy and wastewater.